

ACCELERATING Europe's leading research infrastructures

TUM-FRM II is a partner of the HORIZON 2020 project ACCELERATE. It started on Jan. 01st, 2017 and will last for 48 months. Its aim is at supporting the long-term sustainability of large scale research infrastructures (RIs) with a special focus on ERICs (European research infrastructure consortia), especially CERIC (Central European research infrastructure consortium) in Trieste, where the project is located and managed.

The project develops frameworks to improve the offer of tailored services to private and public entities, ensuring outreach to new scientific and industrial communities worldwide, and defining common protocols for monitoring and assessing RIs' socio-economic impact. A major focus on capacity building will develop current and future RIs' staff competences. The project is divided into seven work packages:

- WP1 aims at developing policies, methodologies, funding plans and human resources elements with special focus on those using the ERIC model and of CERIC specifically.
- The general objective of WP2 is the development of the RI policies, which will make CERIC more accessible to users (pilots in WP5), compliant with the Open Research Data Pilot. This includes care for harmonisation of policies in the "standard" Open Access calls being based on peer-review evaluation.

- WP3 has the goal to develop policies and procedures for commercial access, to be embodied in sets of model documents, which will be compiled in a handbook suitable for further use by other RIs. The RI partners will organise and attend a number of research-to-business events in order to build and maintain in particular with SMEs. The WP also aims at training technology transfer staff with scientific, legal, and economic backgrounds. In WP4, by using the existing contacts of its partner facilities, CERIC will identify scientific communities in European countries like Ukraine, Albania, Serbia etc., to increase its outreach.
- The WP6 (Communication and Dissemination) establishes a two-way dialogue between the project and the project's main stakeholders, as well as among the project partners themselves. The principal objective is to promote CERIC credit with stakeholders, enhance the trust of users, industrial sector, and EC as a reliable partner. In addition, these communication measures will support the exchange of best practice among RIs, both in the partnership and out.
- The WP Management (WP7) ensures the smooth execution of the project from start to the end.

TUM-FRM II will contribute to WPs 1, 2, and 6.

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Participants of the Kick-off meeting visiting the ELETTRA Synchrotron facility. (© Roberto Barnabà, CERIC-ERIC)